

Analysis of emphasizing jute product exports instead of jute raw material exports from Bangladesh

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Abstract

Moving with the nature, we terrestrials are trying to build up a sustainable world in the existing planet. However, jute is not a new name to sustainability, it has created a new horizon to establish the desire green world. Nowadays, the scope is increasing for exporting the jute products instead of raw jute in Bangladesh. The purpose of this paper is determined to analyze the Bangladeshi jute product in the world sustainable market, identify the knowledge gap and analyze of emphasizing on exporting jute product instead of raw jute from Bangladesh. This paper aims to determine future potential of jute product and demand of sustainable product around the world. This research does not give any specific model but it will show a budding possibility which can be grabbed. Though there are so many studies happened but this paper will depict the image in a broader scale. Desk research and in-depth interviews were used to conduct the entire investigation. As a result, there is both primary and secondary data. Additionally, Descriptive statistics are mentioned in the study and analyzed accordingly.

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Introduction

World moves faster than the nature, it badly impacts on climate as the consequence. In order to moving with the nature, it is a challenge for human to build up a sustainable world in the planet. To establish the desire green world, the usages of jute products are increasing. So it is high time for Bangladesh to think and find out the scopes for exporting jute product instead of raw jute (Akter, Sadekin, & Islam, 2020). According to existing studies, the jute sector plays a major influence in the Bangladeshi economy. Jute is an important industry from an economic, agricultural, industrial, and commercial standpoint. Furthermore, they gave the state of information showing the country is capable of manufacturing various types of jute goods that are also ecologically beneficial. Jute was previously known as the "Golden Fiber" of Bangladesh. In industrialized nations, a large potential worldwide market for these jute-made products is being established. To transform these prospective markets into actual markets, Bangladesh must engage in extensive market promotion. Nonetheless, while having the potential, the country is not the greatest at making jute items.

Background of the study

The investigation was performed against the backdrop of jute's growing importance. Despite numerous obstacles and constraints, the research concludes that the jute industry has enormous potential for smallholders and the broader economy of Bangladesh due to an increasing market, both locally and worldwide (D.Net, 2011). The study also focused on identifying the obstacles to expanded production of high-quality jute in Bangladesh, which has enormous potential for catering to a rising market. After extensive desk study, short-listing, and rating, jute emerged as one of the two most promising industries in Bangladesh immediately following the RMG.

The current state of the industry does not reflect a ray of light, as jute mills are closing and there are numerous issues in the Jute industry in Bangladesh, such as a lack of scientific and research knowledge, market tools, a lack of quality seeds, inaccurate market forecasting, and, most importantly, a focus on exporting jute product rather than raw jute. Thus, the major objective of this research is to evaluate the competitive advantage of Bangladeshi jute products in the global market and why Bangladesh should place a greater emphasis on jute products rather than raw jute exports. In addition, the secondary goal is to investigate the feasibility of this objective.

Literature Review

Many scholarly publications on jute production, jute contribution, and jute marketing, particularly in Bangladesh, agreed on the total contribution of exporting jute product to the economy, as well as the potentiality and need for jute-made products. On the other hand, as a result of the epidemic, the demand for sustainable and bio-degradable products is increasing, which is a positive indication. Some current literatures on this subject are discussed below. In this epidemic era, sustainable product demand is rising. In a poll, 72 percent indicated people are paying attention to whether a firm operates in a climate-friendly manner, with 65 percent believing it is critical that the items or services they buy do not hurt the environment (Circular, 2020). Whereas a sizable proportion of customers (52%) modified their habits in this manner. The trend was also evident among millennials (those currently in their twenties and thirties), with more than half (54 percent) stating they now buy more from green firms – but, the research reveals that people of all ages are now seeking more sustainable items.

In terms of recurring business and recommendations, more than three-quarters (78%) indicated they were more inclined to suggest a company if they knew it made a concerted effort

to be environmentally friendly. Another study investigates the market possibility or fare potential of improved jute goods in Bangladesh (Peu, 2019). With an earlier talk about the Jute Diversified Product (JDP) business's past history and market condition, this research sought to represent the general scenario of the Jute Diversified Product (JDP) market potential. He discovered that this region accounted for around 5% of total foreign trade income and 4% of the country's GDP. According to Muzahidul et al (2016), Bangladesh produces the highest grade raw jute in the world, and Bangladesh has a particular competency in raw jute production due to its geological position and ecological comparative advantage.

According to one study, Bangladesh has enormous potential and a vast scope in creating diverse jute products in the global jute sector (World Bank). In comparison to Bangladesh, India has the first mover advantage in creating diverse jute fashion goods. However, India obtains raw jute from Bangladesh. The diversified jute sector may be revitalized and the golden fiber reclaimed. Entrepreneurs must understand the purchasing behavior of various jute goods in order to develop successful green marketing strategies and practices based on these characteristics. Another market research was performed to analyze Bangladesh's jute in the world market, focusing on its present position and potential (Chowdhury & Rashed, 2015). They claim that the demand for jute products is rising in both the foreign and domestic markets, creating a new opportunity for jute in Bangladesh. The study's contribution is to examine Bangladesh's relative growth and advancement. Because of many environmental problems such as global warming and pollution, consumer ecological consciousness has grown exponentially in the twenty-first century (Luzio & Lemke, 2013). Another set of studies stated that marketing managers have prioritized customer requirements and are familiar with environmentally friendly or green products (Follows & Jobber, 2000).

In previous research there are lots of studies with technological side of jute, jute exporting value, raw jute exporting, internal jute producing facts and economic value of jute product from Bangladesh. But there is a gap on emphasizing jute product exporting instead of raw jute, whereas it would be more profitable and Bangladesh is much capable of fulfilling global demand. We want to investigate the following research questions (i) Is there adequate demand of jute product in sustainable world market? (ii) Is Bangladesh capable of fulfilling the world demand of jute product? & (iii) Why should Bangladesh emphasize on exporting jute product instead of raw jute?

Research methodology

Desk research and in-depth conversations on standard and quantitative data are used to conduct comprehensive research. A lot of secondary data are collected from government website, articles, published research papers, newspapers, blogs and so on. The secondary data involved reviewing existing literature on the industry. Both primary and secondary data helped us to draw the map of core processes. The study opens with a brief overview of Bangladesh's jute sector, which is notable for more than simply exports. It also highlights the difficulties, possibilities, and potential solutions for addressing Bangladesh jute production in the global market rather than jute materials. Throughout the study, the identification of knowledge gaps, which is at the heart of research, is obvious.

Discussions and Data analysis

Sustainability and Jute Made Product

Jute is a tall, well-drained plant that grows mostly in Bangladesh and India. What we call jute are really fibers extracted from the plant's epidermis and stem. Because of its hue and commercial worth, it is referred to as "gold fiber." After harvesting, the strands of jute fibers are twisted into solid threads. Burlap is a fabric that you may be familiar with. Jute is environmentally friendly and long-lasting since it takes minimal assistance to grow and fill. When compared to cotton, for example, it requires less water to live and, as previously said, there is no chemical interference. However, jute has a plethora of other environmental benefits, which we shall mention below: The soil matures quickly (4 to 6 months), producing enormous crops for the size of the region where humans grow. As a result, jute is renewable.

Because jute grows more efficiently than other crops, we require less area to produce it; hence, we do not need to extend and intrude on natural habitats and ecosystems with our agricultural activities. We may produce and harvest jute on the same plot of land because jute improves soil fertility for future crops (either jute or other crops). Because jute thrives in tropical locations, it is reliant on natural rains to thrive. Aside from the lack of irrigation, locals typically pick jute and remove the jute fibers by hand, minimizing the need for energy-intensive, unsustainable industrial procedures. Jute is a biodegradable (it dissolves naturally in 1 to 2 years) and compostable fiber. Jute goods survive the test of time and are resistant to wear and tear because the fibers are very robust and sturdy. As a result, jute tote bags and burlap shopping bags are currently popular reusable items as part of the global campaign against plastic. The jute plant absorbs carbon dioxide and emits oxygen at a rate that is many times greater than that of trees. During a typical jute season, one hectare of jute plants may absorb around 15 tons of CO₂ and release 11 tons of oxygen, according to some estimates. While it is currently underutilized, the woody core of the jute plant has the potential to provide the majority of the world's wood demands. Raw green jute, while underutilized, is a great material for creating paper. Jute crops provide new locations and communities with access to new work possibilities and improved food supplies. In other words, transporting meals and other commodities may become even more sustainable as jute eliminates the need for unsustainable storage and transportation options. Jute farming really improves soil fertility for future crops. Jute fiber is a recyclable material. Jute bags are durable and may be reused, eliminating the need for plastic carrying bags.

Why Jute is the best choice

The current chronology of Bangladeshi exported products and worldwide movement throughout the pandemic indicates the finest opportunity for us to alleviate the global market's sustainable supply. Bangladesh, on the other hand, is a wholesome jute production country, but not at its finest. The yearly jute production figures are available here-

Table 1.1: Top Jute Producing Countries in all over the world by rank.
Jute production area of major jute producing countries area (in thousand hectares)

Year	Bangladesh	India	China	Nepal	Myanmar	Thailand
2017-18	715.33	746.7	11.5	8.01	1.26	0.57
2016-17	696.05	754	12.22	8.01	1.28	0.5
2015-16	664.89	742	13.44	8.64	1.29	0.6
2014-15	656.8	818	14.42	11.35	1.67	0.74
2013-14	665.74	837	17.1	11.3	1.02	1
2012-13	680	901	19.3	10.6	3.5	1.3
2011-12	620.2	905	19.3	10.6	8.2	1.4
2010-11	587	900	18.8	13.1	12.6	1.4
2009-10	485.8	773.7	24	11.7	9.6	1.3
2008-09	408.1	785.6	26.2	11.6	14.3	1.4
2007-08	500	9552	33	11.7	20.4	1.2
2006-07	533.4	931	31	12	46.5	2.3
2005-06	466	931	31.1	12.2	41	3.1
2004-05	418	916	32	11.8	35.4	16.6
2003-04	499.8	1000	41	11.9	44.1	20.4
2002-03	436.2	1025	56	11.7	58.7	27.2
2001-02	519.6	986	52	11.3	53.5	19.2
2000-01	448	873	50	14.5	31	19.2

Source: Food and Agricultural Organization

Sector wise Analysis and comparative analysis with jute RMG

According to Bangladesh Garment Exporters and Manufacturers Association (BGMEA), in fiscal year of 2018-'19 Bangladesh total exported US\$34133.27 million with the growth rate of 11.49. Drawbacks due to Coronavirus -Middle of the April 2020, 1145 out of 4621 factories reported US\$3.17 billion order cancellation due to pandemic disaster of fashion-apparel business, according to BGMEA. Fashion-apparel brands are in deficit plus shutting down business. For example, Debenhams declared bankruptcy, JC Penny went out of business, and Zara shuttered up to 1200 fashion outlets throughout the world (Jolly, 2020).

Pharmaceuticals

According to data from the Export Promotion Bureau (EPB), medicine shipments to Bangladesh increased by 25.60 percent to \$ 130 million in FY19, up from \$ 103.46 million the previous year. Barriers - Approximately 60% of the country's artificial products are imported from China, with the remaining 30% imported from India (Uddin J. , 2020).

Leather and Leather Goods

The shipping of leather and leather items was showing tremendous potential, but it has also continued to fall due to a lack of demand from customers who are shifting to substitutes for leather due to changes in trend. According to EPB, leather and leather products sales decreased 10.78 percent year on year to \$559 million between July and January of the current fiscal year.

Frozen and live fish

Shipments of frozen and live fish, including shrimp and crabs, increased 1.58 percent to \$500.4 million. Drawbacks-According to the Bangladesh Frozen Foods Exporters Association, the

frozen fish industry experienced order cancellations of \$597.78 million from buyers, primarily in western nations, during the month of June as the coronavirus epidemic nearly wiped out their economy (BFFEA).

Jute

First and foremost, it is economically viable for Bangladesh. Because Bangladesh has its own plantation for acquiring raw materials, it is also able to satisfy the lead time. On the other hand, Bangladesh has a unique geographical advantage for manufacturing high-quality jute fiber. In the 2018-19 fiscal year, Bangladesh exported ready-made garments worth \$34.13 billion while importing 69 lakh bales of cotton. In 2018-19, the country produced lakhs of jute bales while earning just \$816.27 million from raw jute and jute goods exports (Source: BJRI & EPB). Bangladesh generates \$511.73 million by exporting jute and jute items throughout the first six months of the current fiscal year (July-December), which is 26.3 percent more than the previous year and around 20 percent higher than the objective (Islam).

Historical Analysis of Production and Export of Jute Products

- In 2018, about 3.9 million tons of jute and jute-like fibers were produced, a 2.4 percent rise over the previous year, for a total gain of 1.8 percent over the preceding twelve years.
- In 2018, jute output averaged \$ 2.7 billion at export prices. From 2007 through 2018, total output rose at an annual rate of +1.8% on average. (Today, Global jute market 2019 – Despite a drop in recent years, Bangladesh continues to dominate exports, 2020)

Table 2.1: Trends in Jute Exports in Bangladesh (in Millions of Dollars)

	FY19	FY18	FY17	FY16	FY15	FY14	FY13	FY12	FY11
Jute	832.15	1,023.07	961.60	913.78	865.57	798.96	1,020.36	950.43	1,071.28
Total (Goods)	41,204.02	36,668.20	34,655.90	34,257.18	31,208.95	30,186.62	27,027.45	24,302.00	22,928.20
Jute (% of total)	2.01	2.79	2.77	2.67	2.77	2.65	3.78	3.91	4.67

Source: Bangladesh Bank and EPB (BD Bank and EPB , 2019)

Fulfilling Sustainable World's condition in Bangladeshi Jute Industry:

According to unofficial data, Bangladesh now has thirty authorized industries, eighty are being processed, and about two hundred and eighty are applying (today, 2019). Seven of the top ten LEED certified factories in the world are in Bangladesh (Correspondent, 2020). Bangladesh generated 21941 million US dollars by exporting jute and jute products between July and September of this year, a 3.6 percent increase over the previous quarter (Correspondent, 2020). India (2.1 million tons) and Bangladesh (1.6 million tons) produced the most jute in 2018, accounting for 93 percent of world output. Despite recent declines, Bangladesh continues to dominate exports (Textile Today, 2019). Bangladesh has the highest growth rate in jute output among the main producing countries between 2007 and 2018. (Correspondent, 2020).

Dominating World Market's Demand by Own Raw Material of Jute

Bangladesh leads the global jute export structure, reaching 229K tons in 2018, accounting for about 79 percent of overall exports. India (2.1 million tons) and Bangladesh (1.6 million tons) produced the most jute in 2018, accounting for 93 percent of world output (Textile Today, 2019). According to BSS, the export of jute and jute-made items increased by 21.55 percent in the first half (July-Dec) period of the current fiscal year (FY20), fetching \$511.73 million more than the strategic export objective of \$400.72 million for the period (Express, 2020). Bangladesh has the highest growth rate in terms of jute output among the main producing countries from 2007 to 2018. (Correspondent, 2020).

Export of Jute goods by Bangladesh

Year	Export value (in core taka)	Export (in Lakh MT)
2005-06	2024.10	4.95
2006-07	2215.30	4.71
2007-08	2526.70	5.34
2008-09	2050.00	4.82
2009-10	3963.54	5.77
2010-11	4569.42	4.79
2011-12	5174.00	6.69
2012-13	6162.62	8.68
2013-14	5224.21	8.08
2014-15	5602.16	8.18
2015-16	6240.00	8.25
2016-17	6430.60	8.04
2017-18	6801.57	8.27
2018-19	5220.85	7.3

Source: Department of Jute, Bangladesh

Going for Jute-made Product instead of exporting Raw Jute

Bangladesh is capable of meeting the lead time by obtaining their own jute raw material. From 2007 to 2018, Bangladesh's exports "decreased at an average yearly pace of -8.0 percent." Actually, this is a good indication. Because Bangladesh is increasingly exporting more jute made products rather than raw jute, it is now the buyer's second choice after China (Economics, 2020).

Wonky Scenario within Chinese Product Importers and Our Tactic

The United States is the leading importer of Chinese jute products. Belgium, the Netherlands, Turkey, Germany, Egypt, and other countries are at the top. Nonetheless, China is in jeopardy. Manufacturers in the United States are moving production to other countries in order to dodge tariffs of up to 25% on \$250 billion in Chinese imports (Thomas, 2019). Because of Covid-19, the situation in other importing nations is tense. Companies in the United States, Canada, Europe, and Australia are privately requesting that their supply chain teams find alternative sources that are totally independent of China (Govindarajan & Bagla, 2020). But, Bangladesh remains healthy to the importing countries- Bangladesh shipped around the world which was approx. US\$45.7 billion worth in 2019, ongoing trade disputes between the USA and China. That dollar amount reflects a 44% increase since 2015 and a 1.4% uptick from 2018 to 2019. (Source: The Independent)

Future of World Jute Market

Alibaba, a significant shopping site, stated that the consumer ecosystem has surpassed \$ 380 million in recent years. Total raw product sales grew by 18% in 2019 compared to 2018. Simultaneously, biodiversity sales have grown from \$4.712 million US in 2015 to \$8.087 million US in 2018. (nielsen, 2018). Jute imports totaled \$197 million in value in 2018. Brands are becoming increasingly concerned with environmentally friendly products. If we continue on our current path, we will require the equivalent of 2.3 planets by 2050, according to footprintnetwork.org. H&M Group establishes jute goods on home furnishing and accessories windows as part of its sustainability plan, with the goal of becoming 100 percent circular and renewable with nature (Today, 2020).

Feasibility Discussion

Bangladesh already has a competitive edge in the global market due to its own materials and low labor costs. Aside from this, there are other possibilities.

Shorter Lead Time with Easy SCM

In generally, Bangladesh has a favor on lead time and supply chain management for having own sourcing of raw material for jute-made product, which helps to minimize the extra time.

Good news is, Bangladeshi government has set a target to cut the time for completing export procedures to one day by 2022 under the National Single Window (NSW) project.

Wholesome Market Demand

For example, according to "Worldwide Sector Trends, Allocation, Size, Growth, Opportunity, and Forecasting for 2019-2024," the global stock market reached US \$ 1.8 Billion in 2018, with a CAGR of around 11.5 percent from 2011 to 2018. (Jordan, 2019).

Previous Hygiene issue blasts vastly due to Covid-19

Uses of the natural fiber is being on the rise worldwide owing to a growing shift towards eco-friendly lifestyles during Covid-19 (news, 2020).

Production Capabilities

Bangladesh already has infrastructure and capabilities to grab this sector. Sonali Aansh Group, Alijan Jute, Janata Aansh, Anwar Specialized Jute Goods, etc. are the example.

Product Feasibility

281 types of jute products are being produced in Bangladesh. Nowadays Bangladesh is producing special carpets to the sophisticated airplane or luxury car. High quality bags, sacks and home furnishing are being produced for **H&M, M&S, Kid, Zara** etc. giant brands (Source: Textile Today).

Low Labor Cost

Last year, the government set minimum basic wage for the workers of state-owned factories at Tk 8,300 (\$97.44).

Bangladesh is Technically Strong

The nation is producing jute fiber from many years ago. There is not any toughness in dyeing, weaving, cutting or sewing for jute-made product.

Ease of doing Business

There is little improvement in the level compared to previous years 'as of 100, Bangladesh achieved 41.94, which is 0.91% t higher.

Mongla Port and EPZ surrounding a fruitful area for Jute

Mongla EPZ along with port is situated with a port and the next to the fruitful area of jute plantation (Faridpur, Golpagonj, etc.).

Innovation

"If tin can be made with jute, it is possible to make a bicycle too," Many of us do not know that Bangladesh is one of the top five countries in bicycles exports to Denmark (Uddin M., 2020). Making polybags by jute is another innovation in Bangladesh. These innovations give us a standard in world market.

Non-Price Factors Affecting Competitiveness of Jute and Hard Fibers and Polypropylene

The technical aspects seem to be important to end use. Extremely strong impact and impact, low weight, non-abrasive ability and water resistance are major characteristics of polypropylene. Jute bags have changed a lot in product packaging, especially in chemical and industrial products as this requires water proof. Breathing, on the other hand, is required for packaging plants and fruits. In such circumstances, jute bags are preferable. Polypropylene is often used in automatic bag filling systems, which a jute bag does not have. The use of jute bags in food items is further hampered by rising health and hygiene issues caused by dust and

debris. Importers occasionally complain about the quality of jute ropes, citing concerns such as inequity, bad knots, and inappropriate packing (UNCTAD).

Factor	Jute and Hard Fibres	Polypropylene
Technical Characteristics	(+) breathability (jute bags)	(+) strong tensile strength and resilience to impact
	(+) biodegradability and reusability	(+) light weight
	(+) natural look	(+) not shrinkable, rot-proof, and water resistant
	(-) Dust and tiny fibers are present.	(-) flammability and smoke toxicity dangers
	(-) incompatibility with automated filling systems	
Quality	(-) occasional problems	(+) consistent quality
Reliabilities of supplies	(-) Instability of supply owing to weather conditions and long-distance transportation	(+) regular production and supplies possible at short notice.
Marketing	(-) a lack of a well-organized marketing structure	(+) aggressive marketing strategies

Source: UNCTAD (1996)

Note: (+) stands for positive quality; and (-) stands for negative quality.

Responses from Industry Experts (One to one interview)

Questions	Answer from experts	Remarks
Is jute important for sustainable world development?	Yes	There could be a demand of jute product in sustainable market
Could jute be a weapon to reduce harmful products for environment?	Yes	Jute is good as a ecofriendly product
Jute product exporting scope for Bangladesh, put your valuable explanation, please.	It's a huge scope. The world market demand for jute product is growing day by day. Its blessing for Bangladesh, as the best raw jute producing country. We already have some renowned buyers like H&M, M&S. We should emphasize on product manufacturing by own jute.	Its high time to emphasize on product manufacturing by own raw jute.
Which one is important- raw jute exporting or jute product exporting, and why?	Obviously going for product instead of exporting it as raw, would be more profitable for us.	Jute product is more profitable.
What are the strengths for Bangladesh to export jute product instead of exporting raw jute?	Lead time and cost is less, because of own raw materials than the rivals, our jute friendly land. We have also industrial experts, as we lead the RMG.	We found our strengths.
What about the global jute product market?	It's simply growing.	Our experts are known with jute world market.
Is it possible to produce best seed in Bangladesh?	Yes, if that field is open for us. (BADC experts said)	We could emphasize on making own seed instead of importing it from India.
Feasibility of jute as a component to manufacture bulk product, tell about it, please.	We are leading a huge RMG production zone. Again, we have some giant jute product manufacturing factory like Sonali Aansh, Janata Aansh. So, yes it is so much feasible for us.	Jute product manufacturing feasibility is alright.
Is Bangladesh capable of fulfilling global jute products demand?	Yes, by process. (means- step by step)	No lacking in capability.
What do you think about supply chain map for jute production in Bangladesh?	Yes, it's important. South zone of our country (like-Gopalganj, Faridpur, Madaripur) is good for jute cultivation, and the Mongla Port is next to there. So, there could design an economic zone only for jute product manufacturing factories.	It could design an economic zone only for jute product manufacturing factories.

Key findings

Value added jute products have huge demand around the globe, where Bangladesh could be an opportunity taker. Bangladesh is now the second-biggest jute producer, with India being the greatest. However, due to excellent temperature and soil conditions, Bangladesh produces the

highest-grade jute. Therefore, this is absolutely a competitive advantage for us. On top of that, the demand for sustainable product is increasing whereas jute made product is biodegradable. So, demand for jute made product in western countries is increasing day by day. Moreover, Statistics shows that Bangladesh is exporting jute made product each year and we can see a positive trend. However, we need more diversification in product, because there is a huge scope in this market. Additionally, Shorter lead time, technical knowledge and low labor cost make this more viable. As interviewed with veterans, we found some limitations. Such as, poor SME policy from government and NGO side, awareness within owners should be grown (means-awareness in ecofriendly manufacturing), need an economic zone for jute production beyond the RMG.

Limitations of the study

Due to the pandemic, it was difficult to get permission from some primary data source to meet. Because of lockdown situation, it was kind of possible for us to roam, visit physically and talk with the people. Due to privacy, it could not be possible to visit the top-level jute product manufacturers like Sonali Aansh, Janta Aansh. Sometimes it was found some incomplete secondary data. It is a matter of great sorrow that while doing our research paper, we hardly find any related paper. Lack of concern on this sector is visible. Due to financial shortage, it could not be possible to collect some secondary data by paying. As we did not get any fund, so it was another tough task for us to accumulate information for other sites like Index box as it is paid site. Due to fund, we could not access those sites.

Theory based marketing and promotional model.

Conclusion

To transform these prospective markets into actual markets, Bangladesh must engage in extensive market promotion. A number of R&D projects and programs have been conducted, resulting in the development of new technologies for the production of diverse jute products. Nonetheless, while having the potential, the country is not the greatest at making jute items. By focusing on the previously indicated guidelines, the market may be able to catch up. According to the facts of the green globe, it is an extraordinary and expanding industry, particularly for the manufacturing country of Bangladesh. However, the business must meet rising market demand for higher-quality jute products. Farmers must obtain a better price by understanding their fiber grade and related pricing, as well as obtain good quality seed for increased harvests. Wherever possible, excellent seed should be gathered locally rather than imported from India. Furthermore, jute mills with access to commercial bank financing might increase demand for raw jute.

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Appendix

Interview Questions:

1. Is jute important for sustainable world development?
2. Could jute be a weapon to reduce harmful products for environment?
3. Jute product exporting scope for Bangladesh, put your valuable explanation, please.
4. Which one is important- raw jute exporting or jute product exporting, and why?
5. What are the strengths for Bangladesh to export jute product instead of exporting raw jute?
6. What about the global jute product market?
7. Is it possible to produce best seed in Bangladesh?
8. Feasibility of jute as a component to manufacture bulk product, tell about it, please.
9. Is Bangladesh capable of fulfilling global jute products demand?
10. Is Bangladesh technically capable of making highly finished jute products?
11. What do you think about supply chain map for jute production in Bangladesh?
12. Is there any internal pros and cons involved with jute manufacturing supply chain and value chain where can be developed or changed to be the best in exporting?

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